

Archiving, sharing and discussing research data on Eastern Europe, South Caucasus and Central Asia

Data Review

Data Citation

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Abstract

The Armed Conflict Location & Event Data Project (ACLED) is a project created by Clionadh Raleigh (University of Sussex) that is operating as a non-profit, non-governmental organization since 2014 (1). The ACLED is a disaggregated data collection listing political violence and protest events around the world (ACLED 2019: 8), covering the timespan from 1997 to the present day (6). The ACLED research team defines political violence as: “[...] the use of force by a group with a political purpose or motivation, or with distinct political effects.” (ACLED 2019: 8). The dataset was designed to provide a comprehensive overview of political disorder around the world (ACLED 2019: 8). As of summer 2024, the data collection is continuing, with the dataset consistently being reviewed and updated on a weekly basis. For the Europe and Central Asia region covered by Discuss Data, the dataset contains 400.000+ entries. The Discuss Data relevant country coverage begins in 2018 and includes the following countries: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Russia, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Ukraine and Uzbekistan (ACLED 2019: 3). Which together total around 236.000 entries. The data review contains a link leading to the official ACLED website from which the dataset, as well as additional information about the dataset in the form of a codebook and other descriptive texts are available for download. The download of the dataset requires a free registration on the ACLED website.

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Data Review - The Armed Conflict Location & Event Data Project

The Armed Conflict Location & Event Data Project (ACLED) is a project created by Clionadh Raleigh that is operating as a non-profit, non-governmental organization since 2014 (1). The ACLED is a disaggregated data collection listing political violence and protest events around the world (ACLED 2019: 8), covering the timespan from 1997 to the present day (6). The ACLED research team defines political violence as follows: “Political violence is defined as the use of force by a group with a political purpose or motivation, or with distinct political effects.” (ACLED 2019: 8). The dataset was designed to provide a comprehensive overview of political disorder around the world, thus select non-violent events were also included within the dataset in order to capture the potential precursors or critical junctures of a given violent conflict (ACLED 2019: 8).

As of summer 2024 the data collection seems to be continuing with the dataset consistently being reviewed and updated on a weekly basis. For the Europe and Central Asia region the dataset contains 400.000+ entries (ACLED 2019: 3).

The ACLED dataset utilises a system that defines the occurring political disorder by its constituent events, which allows for a comparison of political disorder trends across countries and time periods (ACLED 2019: 8). The fundamental unit of analysis in this system is the event (events involve designated actors, occur at a specific location, and occur on a specific day). ACLED records six different event types:

- I. Battles: “[...] a violent interaction between two organized armed groups at a particular time and location.” (ACLED 2019: 11).
- II. Protests: “[...] an in-person public demonstration of three or more participants in which the participants do not engage in violence, though violence may be used against them.” (ACLED 2019: 13).
- III. Riots: “[...] violent events where demonstrators or mobs of three or more engage in violent or destructive acts, including but not limited to physical fights, rock throwing, property destruction, etc.” (ACLED 2019: 14).
- IV. Explosions/Remote violence: “[...] incidents in which one side uses weapon types that, by their nature, are at range and widely destructive.” (ACLED 2019: 15).
- V. Violence against civilians: “[...] violent events where an organized armed group inflicts violence upon unarmed non-combatants.” (ACLED 2019: 17).
- VI. Strategic developments: “[...] captures contextually important information regarding incidents and activities of groups that are not recorded as ‘Political Violence’ or ‘Demonstrations’ events, yet may trigger future events or contribute to political dynamics within and across states.” (ACLED 2019: 19).

These event types can be divided into 25 sub-event types (both violent and non-violent), which in turn are also categorized into three overarching disorder types: political violence,

demonstrations, and strategic developments. These types are hierarchical, meaning if two different types of events occur within the same context, the higher ranking event type will be recorded (ACLED 2019: 9). For a full list of the sub-event types as well as their hierarchical order please refer to ACLED 2019: 10ff.

As pointed out above, if two different types of actions between the same actors occur on the same day it is recorded as a single aggregate event to avoid double-counting incidents (ACLED 2019: 21). If however, another event type involving different actors occurs on the same day and in the same location, this event will be recorded as a separate entry (ACLED 2019: 22).

Three types of temporal information are recorded in the ACLED dataset: the date of the event, the year it occurred, and a variable describing the temporal precision of the previous 'date' variable using a numeric code between one and three. If the actual date of the event is recorded the 'time_precision' variable will be coded as 1. If the source materials states that the event happened during the week (or a similar period of time) it will be coded as 2. If the source states that the event took place sometime during the month, the time precision is coded as 3. ACLED does not include events with less temporal information (ACLED 2019: 36-37).

Up to six different types of spatial information can be recorded for each coded event:

- I. "The continental sub-region in which the event occurred;
- II. The country in which the event occurred and its associated ISO code;
- III. The name of the first, second, and third level administrative zones in which the specific location is found, according to GIS-based assessments and updated administrative codes;
- IV. The name of the specific location of an event;
- V. The geographic coordinates of that specific location; and
- VI. A spatial precision code." (ACLED 2019: 35).

ACLED does not include events that are imprecise to the country level. Such reports will be investigated until more accurate information is found (ACLED 2019: 36).

The ACLED dataset codes a range of different actors and assigns them an 'Inter'code which categorizes them by whether they have similar organizational structures, goals, or practices as other actors. Thus, offering a way to determine how patterns of activity conform to goals and organizations. As such however, this variable is subject to change (ACLED 2019: 24). The categories of the 'Inter'code include: state forces, rebels, militias, identity groups, demonstrators, civilians, and external or other forces (ACLED 2019: 23). On top of the 'Inter'code ACLED also includes a joined 'Interaction' code, which combines the two 'Inter'codes associated with the two main actors of a given event, enabling an easy overview of the parties associated with a conflict (ACLED 2019: 29).

Other variables within the dataset include: civilian targeting (states whether civilians were targeted), reported fatalities, notes (short description of the event), and tags (which “[...] provide a flexible means of refining or grouping existing variables, or providing new variables for specific contexts that are not already captured within the other data columns.” [ACLED 2019: 38]) (ACLED 2019: 37ff). For a detailed list on the tags included in the dataset please refer to ACLED 2024 “Tags in the Data”.

The official ACLED website offers options to filter the data by using the ACLED Explorer in the ‘Explorer’ section. Here, the user can filter the data by the type of event, type of actor, type of interaction, actors, location or time period. The results of the customized search can then be viewed in either a tabular view, or alternatively in the form of a chart (1).

The ACLED dataset collects its information from four main types of sources: (a) traditional media (subnational, national, regional and international media outlets), (b) reports (by international institutions and non-governmental organizations), (c) local partner data, and (d) new media (e.g. Twitter, Telegram, WhatsApp), though this last source is not used for scraping large amounts of data but rather utilised in a targeted manner while verifying the collected information (ACLED 2019: 38-39).

It is to note however, that the research team customizes their sources according to the country in question and its unique geography, freedom of press and types of violence. Since “[o]nly a tailor-made sourcing process for individual regions/countries will make data more reliable.” (ACLED 2023: 3). One practice the research team focuses on during this customization is the prioritization of local data since this prioritization in particular seems to increase reliability (ACLED 2023: 4).

The research team also puts a large emphasis on their reviewing process. Each week the ACLED team performs three tasks:

- I. Sourcing and reviewing source material
- II. Collecting and inputting data
- III. Cleaning and reviewing those data and sources

As the team states: “These reviews are crucial because as time passes more information may surface about additional conflict events.” (ACLED 2020: 2). One such example of information that might need updating, would be inconsistent reports on the fatalities within a conflict in the immediate aftermath of said conflict, since information is often sparse or biased in during that time (ACLED 2020: 2).

Discuss Data relevant country coverage:

Country	Number of Entries
Armenia	6.831
Azerbaijan	18.893

Belarus	3.928
Estonia	379
Georgia	4.472
Kazakhstan	4.891
Kyrgyzstan	2.101
Latvia	264
Lithuania	434
Moldova	1.796
Russia	21.339
Tajikistan	173
Turkmenistan	48
Ukraine	170.150
Uzbekistan	949

Sources:

- (1) ACLED – Armed Conflict Location & Event Data Website. <https://acleddata.com/>. Last accessed 27.09.2024.
- (2) ACLED. 2019. “ACLED Codebook, 2019.” *Armed Conflict Location & Event Data Project (ACLED)*. <https://acleddata.com/knowledge-base/codebook>. Last accessed 27.09.2024.
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- (6) ACLED. ACLED Coverage to Date. https://acleddata.com/acleddatanew/wp-content/uploads/dlm_uploads/2019/01/ACLED_Country-and-Time-Period-coverage_updFeb2020.pdf?fbclid=IwAR381teUbVOI4XCw9ji-JkfXnK7gpKEguAX_kJpPkTmEvXfZ_7WaX4nn4dA. Last accessed 27.09.2024.